

New EMPIR project – Metrology for Drug Delivery

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ABSTRACT

This document presents the scientific and technical objectives, state of the art and expected progress beyond it, and most importantly the expected impact on metrology, science, standards, and society of the new joint research project - MeDD II, Metrology for Drug Delivery (follow up of project MeDD I). It was selected for funding through the EURAMET EMPIR program of the European Commission and the participating countries. The project started in June 2019 and will last for three years. It involves 15 partners from National and Designated Metrology Institutes, companies, and academia. The main objective is to enable traceable measurements of volume, flow and pressure of existing drug delivery devices (like infusion pumps and analysers) and inline sensors that work at flow rates lower than 100 nL/min, in order to prevent inaccurate measurement results. This project will also investigate fast changing flow rates, liquid mixing behaviour and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems with the purpose of improving dosing accuracy in each infusion line.

1. Introduction

The most commonly used form of therapy in the hospital environment is infusion therapy [1], which implies that drug delivery is a critical aspect in health safety. Because of the widespread application by many users in critical health situations, infusion errors are often made, with potential dramatic effects in the patients. There are various examples where adverse incidents, morbidity and even mortality, can be traced back to poor drug delivery. The authors Snijder et al. [2] published a review in which medical errors associated with flow rate variability in infusion devices are described; this emphasized the severe and lasting health damage that has occurred.

A well-defined metrological infrastructure is needed to allow infusion pump manufacturers to include robust information on the “real” dose delivered to the patient, and users of drug delivery devices to have an enhanced metrological knowledge of these critical devices, thus preventing incorrect measurements and significantly improving patient safety.

Metrology can bridge the knowledge gap by designing a representative multi-infusion intravenous system for investigating how different liquids mix and how this affects drugs concentrations. The increasing

uptake of novel microfluidic applications in healthcare require the development of a metrological infrastructure for validating quality and reproducibility [3].

The new Joint Research Project - MeDD II, Metrology for Drug Delivery, funded under the EMPIR program of the European Commission started in June 2019, will last for three years involving 15 partners, including: nine National and Designated Metrology Institutes (IPQ - Portugal, CETIAT - France, CMI - Chez Republic, DTI - Denmark, METAS - Switzerland, NEL - United Kingdom, NQIS - Greece, RISE - Sweden and KRISS - Korea), four companies (DNV GL - The Netherlands, HSG-IMIT - Germany, INESC MN - Portugal, BHT - The Netherlands) and two University Hospitals (THL - Germany, UMCU - The Netherlands).

This project is coordinated by IPQ, Portuguese Institute of Quality, and has the overall aim to improve dosing accuracy and enable traceable measurements of volume, flow and pressure of existing drug delivery devices and inline sensors operating at very low flow rates (lower than 100 nL/min). This can be achieved through the development of new calibration methods and improved metrological infrastructures. Another goal of this project is to investigate the influence of: different flow rate regimes, physical properties of the infused fluids (e.g. viscoelasticity), and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems. This knowledge

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will help preventing inaccurate measurement results and thus improve patient safety.

2. State of the art and progress beyond it

In 2004, in a metrological effort to understand and improve multi-infusion, Clark [4] defined the crucial performance aspect of an infusion system and established the importance of a patient receiving the correct dose, of the required substances, in a certain time. However, in multi-infusion, this is not an easy task. The first steps towards a better understanding of the real flow rates and of the drugs' concentration delivered to the patient were made in two previous projects [5,6]. In MeDD I (Metrology for Drug Delivery I) [5] the aim was to prevent errors by upgrading calibration services and improving knowledge transfer to the end-user [5]. An infrastructure, consisting of traceable calibration services for drug delivery systems for flow rates down to 100 nL/min, was developed in five European National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) [7, 8]. Syringe pumps and peristaltic pumps with accessories were tested [9]. In general, manufacturers declare an accuracy of 5% for these instruments, these values were validated by the project. Additionally, the effects of variations in several physical parameters in infusion systems were incorporated in a predictive model [10].

This new project will go beyond the research conducted during the project MeDD I [5] by investigating the influence of fast changing flow rates due to a change in the pre-set flow rate. Also, a multi-infusion setup will be developed to investigate fluid flow rates and fluid compositions in the outlet of the infusion line. This setup will allow the assessment of the performance of drug delivery devices in multi-infusion systems and the determination of the concentration of each drug being administered.

3. Scientific objectives

The overall goal is to enable traceable measurements of volume, flow and pressure of existing drug delivery devices and inline sensors that work at a flow rate lower than 100 nL/min. This project will also investigate different flow rate regimes, liquid mixing behaviour and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems with the purpose of improving dosing accuracy in each infusion line.

The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop new traceable techniques for generating and measuring the response time or delay time against changes in flow rate, in the interval from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min, using Newtonian liquids, for example, optical methods.
2. To upgrade the existing flow facilities and knowledge of the participant NMIs in order to enable traceable inline measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids, as a function of the flow rate and pressure drop, with a target relative uncertainty of 2% ($k = 2$).
3. To develop and validate novel calibration procedures for existing drug delivery devices traceable to a primary standard and a target relative uncertainty of 2% for a range of 5 nL/min up to 600 mL/min. In addition, to develop a proof-of-concept of an on-chip microfluidic pump used as transfer standard in drug discovery and organ-on-a-chip applications in the flow rates from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min.
4. To design and develop a multi infusion system containing check valves, with several options for testing the miscibility of liquids (with different viscosities and flow rates) and how this affects drugs' concentration.
5. To facilitate the take up of the technology and measurement infrastructure developed in the project by the measurement supply chain, (i.e. accredited laboratories, instrumentation manufacturers, etc.), standards developing organizations and end-users (i.e. hospitals and health centres).

4. Impact

4.1. Society and health sectors

The main goal of this project is to improve diagnostics, patient treatment and patient safety by developing new calibration methods, resulting in a robust traceability chain for flow rate measurements performed by several drug delivery devices such as multi infusion systems, insulin pumps and pain controllers working at flow rates as low as 100 nL/min. It is known that drug errors account for a significant percentage of medical errors, with dosing errors being a significant subset of them [11–14]. Depending on the drug type, the patient characteristics and the applied therapy, dosing errors can have severe consequences, including a substantial number of fatalities.

A better understanding on how dosing errors may occur, and how to increase the accuracy of the drug delivery devices will have a noticeable impact on the health industry and significantly improve patient treatment and safety. Therefore, any attempt to prevent adverse events by improving the knowledge on actual doses can already make an enormous difference for the individual patient, especially newborn babies, and have a significant impact on the health sector as a whole. A considerable impact on society through improved patient safety can be expected by improving the calibration and administration conditions for drug delivery devices and setups. Important examples can be found in chemotherapy, in anaesthesia, in the operating theatre and in nursery wards, especially for the neonates. The calibration methods are also important in drug injection applications in very small anatomic regions of the body, for example, in the inner ear. Improving metrology for microfluidic methods in this field could help to find new horizons for the treatment of acute deafness and Meniere's disease.

Furthermore, occlusion alarms' quality can be improved, and occlusion alarm fatigue diminished by more reliable pressure measurements.

Accurate drug delivery will also have economic benefits. In modern medicine, many sophisticated pharmaceuticals are available, but only at high prices. Metrology can help prevent waste of expensive medication, by enabling the delivery of accurate dosage.

Finally, the infusion pumps analysers used by the hospitals' maintenance to calibrate the in-house used infusion devices need to be calibrated against a reference. However, in most of the cases the traceability of these devices are only guaranteed in hospitals with ISO 9001 certification since it is mandatory.

4.2. Metrology

This project will upgrade various existing facilities for flow measurements from 5 nL/min up to 100 nL/min using different Newtonian fluids as the test medium. These new facilities will be validated by means of an inter-comparison with stable transfer standards allowing the recognition of new measurement capabilities.

New calibration methods will be developed based on optical methods and this knowledge will be disseminated across the scientific community by relevant publications in scientific journals and congresses.

These new calibration methods will be beneficial for both accredited laboratories and manufacturers of drug delivery devices. These new procedures can later be updated for microfluidic devices used in health, for example, to advance organ-on-a-chip technology. A calibration guide for the different type of drug delivery devices will be drafted describing the calibration methods, conditions under which they are to be operated, target uncertainty and best working practices. The draft will be submitted to EURAMET and made available to end users.

4.3. Standardisation

In this project, procedures and methods for the calibration of drug delivery devices already on the market are going to be developed. This

information will be supplied to the relevant ISO technical committees (TC). For example, the current version of IEC 60601-2-24 used by manufacturers to develop drug delivery devices and by laboratories and maintenance departments of hospitals to verify and calibrate drug delivery devices, is roughly 20 years old and is outdated. Moreover, the given measurement methods are not suitable for very low flow rates (<100 nL/min) relevant to implantable infusion pumps where applications are encountered. It is widely acknowledged that an update to the measurement procedures for different types of pumps and master calibrators is required. It is envisaged that the project will impact on Section Eight of IEC 60601-2-24 (Accuracy of operating data and protection against hazardous output).

This project can also supply inputs on the Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 5, 2017 on medical devices that are currently lacking information regarding maximum permissible errors of several medical devices, including drug delivery devices.

5. Work package 1 - method developments

The most common calibration method for low flow measuring instruments used by the National Metrology Institutes (NMI) is the gravimetric method; this involves the determination of the liquid mass flow and liquid density. However, there is still the need to scale-down the measurements with the appropriate uncertainty values, and several investigations are now focused on the development of new calibration methodologies using novel and innovative approaches to this challenge based on optical methods.

The main objective of work package 1 is to develop new traceable techniques for generating and measuring flow rate, in the interval from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min, using Newtonian liquids, like optical-based volumetric methods.

5.1. Interferometry

Laser interferometry uses the concept of interference to measure the intensity of a wave resulting from the overlapping of two or more waves that have travelled over different distances and are superimposed on a single point; the difference between the distance travelled is then determined with an accuracy of less than half the wavelength [15]. This technique has been extensively used in the determination of distances due to its high precision and can be adapted to measure flow if the interferometer is used to monitor the distance travelled in a specific time interval by a pusher block of a syringe pump (flow generator) and it is used by IPQ to measure flow rates down to 5 nL/min (Fig. 1).

5.2. – drop measurement

With this technique used by IPQ, the flow is determined by observing the volume increase of a drop, at the end of the tube generated by the instrument under test, by a unit of time. This observation can be performed using photographs taken by a USB-digital microscope (Fig. 2) and the volume of the drop can be determined by optical software applications. If the time of the volume difference is also taken into account, then it is possible to determine the flow.

5.3. – meniscus tracking principle

This method used by CETIAT is based on an optical, non-intrusive and portable measurement system (Figs. 3 and 4). It consists in measuring the displacement with respect to time of a liquid-air interface, inside a glass capillary tube that is connected to a flow generating device. Images of the moving meniscus are acquired by a high-speed camera. A software is used to record the timestamp of each image and to measure the displacements using the *Digital Image Correlation* method. The generated liquid flow rate is determined from the calculated

Fig. 1. IPQ interferometric setup for flow measurements.

Fig. 2. IPQ setup for optical observation of a drop.

Fig. 3. CETIAT Optical meniscus tracking setup for flow measurement.

velocity and the previously measured inner diameter of the capillary.

5.4. –precision linear stage actuator

Due to the limitations of the gravimetric methods at very low flow rates below 100 nL/min, METAS has developed piston provers

Fig. 4. Schematic illustration of the optical meniscus tracking setup at CETIAT.

consisting of a high precision linear stage with a fixed linear measuring system (see Fig. 5). The position of the linear stage is determined by counting the pulses sent by the linear measuring system by means of an FPGA, which is a Field Programmable Gate Array with hard coded program code running on a defined constant cycle time of the order of 25 ns (40 MHz). For each additional pulse in any direction, a time stamp of the FPGA is recorded and a pair with the position and the timestamp is formed. This pair of values is then read from the main software and the real time position can be recorded. The real time speed is then determined by a linear fit of several pairs of position data with the corresponding time stamps as the slope corresponds to the speed. Multiplying the speed with the cross section of the piston gives the volume flow rate. The linear measuring system and the diameter of the piston are traceable to the SI units of length and with the traceable time measurement the measurement method is a volumetric primary standard. Thus, measurements of volumes and volumetric flow rates are traceable to the SI units.

Moreover, fast changing flow rates within seconds can be generated by changing the speed of the linear stage. Any flow rate profile can be generated with flow rates down to 5 nL/min by using pistons of a volume of 50 μ l. Additionally, the volumetric flow generator can calibrate flow devices with process-oriented liquids to enhance the quality of the measurements results of the flow devices during production processes.

6. Conclusion

By improving the flow rate measurement accuracy of drug delivery devices, with the development of new measuring methods, dosing errors will be reduced, and lives will be saved. This can be achieved by wider uptake of traceable calibrations of low and ultra-low flow infusion (master) devices and by improved knowledge of calibrating drug delivery devices in clinical environments, especially in the case of multiple infusion systems. This project directly benefits society by enabling the identification and reduction of dosing errors in drug delivery devices used for patient treatment and diagnostics.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 5. METAS piston prover of the microflow facility, (A) high precision linear stage, (B) linear measuring system, (C) syringe or piston, (D) mounting syringe body, (E) mounting and positioning for piston plunger.

Declaration of competing interest

There is no conflict of interest in this paper.

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